

Use of Innovative Tools for Library Marketing in the University Libraries of Lahore, Pakistan

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Abstract:- The aim of this study was to look into the cutting-edge methods for library marketing with encountered issues by librarians. The urge for marketing in the university libraries of Lahore and the present approaches used by university libraries to promote library and information services, and suggestions for increasing that marketing is encountered in in-depth study. The present study consisted of four objectives including the demand for library service marketing, present strategy on library promotion, the challenges in library marketing and to improve library service promotion including the innovation tools for library marketing. A quantitative research approach and the survey method based on the questionnaire with six main elements was presented through convenience sampling. The data was collected from 127 library professionals through a questionnaire. The present study reported that the marketing of university libraries required strengthening the interpersonal interaction between librarians and users to identify the information needs of users, achieving a high degree of customer loyalty, educating users regarding the achievement of library usage, and accomplishing educating of the library. The findings revealed that respondents adopted social media applications for marketing library services to increase the personal relationship between staff and users. The method used by librarians for marketing including sending letters to users about newly added services through E-mail and text messages, provision of electronic access to information, having the representative in institutional functions for library marketing, and use of leaflets and posters. This study is geographically limited to the university library in Lahore.

Keywords:- Marketing of LIS; Challenges in LIS marketing; Strategies for LIS marketing; Innovative tools.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaboration on library services and expertise in the diversified knowledge landscape of today is crucial. The "hearts" or "nerve centers" of the parent body are academic libraries. University libraries are constantly looking for new ways to reach their customers (Gustafson, Sharrow, and Short, 2017). With the influence of technology and other social developments, the function and definition of library resources are evolving very rapidly. Owing to digital technologies, the variety of programs that take place beyond the actual library is growing. Libraries and information services must employ marketing strategies to

further the priorities, goals, and objectives of the institution if they are to remain competitive in the current market.

A high-tech library or service center might not have been successful without a marketing plan (Eje and Dushu 2018). Ameen (2015) has established that to succeed in a competitive world, any company must adopt the new marketing philosophy and processes used to create consumer loyalty. Marketing is a survival strategy in the information age's competitive challenges. A library's survival depends, among other things, on its parental organization and its visibility to its intended audience. In the context of libraries, marketing is crucial to providing benefits to users, removing barriers to usage and access, persuading and educating users, and actively getting ready to meet their basic needs. The importance of marketing prevents it from being seen as a standalone library feature. The entire library's marketing strategy is crucial. That is the totality of the processes and resources of the library viewed from the viewpoint of the final effect, that is, from the point of perspective of the customer. A library without customers is worthless, and customers have to be kept informed of the advantages of the library in delivering information tools and facilities to be effective. The marketing philosophy deals with the procurement of resources that fulfill the consumer needs and seek to accomplish the aims of the enterprise (Soroya and Ameen, 2013).

Libraries must establish channels to reach customers as effectively as possible in order to draw visitors, pique curiosity among non-users, and increase knowledge of accessible activities and facilities. In order to communicate the availability and significance of such services to specific groups, advertising strategies are employed. These strategies can be design to motivate both library users and non-users to take action (Helinsky, 2014; Yi, 2014). Social networks are used across the globe for several uses in Libraries and Information Centers (Prajapati and Bhavsar, 2018). Xia (2009) stated, "library marketing strategies respond to changes from socio-cultural, political as well as technological conditions of a particular time". Osinulu et al. (2018) stated that Nigerian librarians utilized customer survey studies, textbooks, inter-library loan programs, and increased burrowing rights as a marketing tool for libraries. Khanchandani and Hasan (2016) stated that the IIT Central Library in New Delhi used blogs, user orientation, e-resources, WebOPAC, discovery services, interlibrary services, photographs, and a list of recent arrivals for marketing purposes.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The goal of this study is to investigate fresh marketing strategies for libraries at the university of Lahore. The following goals were set for this study in order to achieve this and maintain a clear understanding of the research aim:

- To capture the demand for library service marketing in academic libraries.
- To study the current techniques used by university libraries in the promotion of their resources and information services.
- To identify challenges that face librarians while marketing university libraries services.
- To investigate the methods to improve the promotion of university library services.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The worth of Library customers was also enhanced after the presentation of five classic laws by Ranganathan. These laws are also significant proof to declare the marketing approach as a part and parcel of library services. A brief description of these laws are “Books are for use”, “Every reader his/her book”, “Every book its reader”, “Save the time of the reader” and “Library is a growing organism”. All five laws are concerned with the Philosophy of LIS marketing declaring transformation of library services with the changes in the World's environment, and accordingly, new technologies should be adopted in library services (Bhatt, 2011).

Kotler and Levy's (1969) publication on 'Broadening the Concept of Marketing' can be considered as the foundation of the idea of utilization of marketing services in Libraries. With time, the concept of non-profit-organizations was grown up into a theory of services marketing that is unswervingly associated with the LIS. Kotler (1988) used the term "Social marketing" for service marketing and defined the term as "the analysis, planning, implementation, and control of carefully formulated programs designed to bring about voluntary exchanges of values with target markets the purpose of achieving organizational objectives”.

Kaba (2011) through his study explored the use of web services by the academic libraries of the United Arab Emirates (UAE) for the promotion of their commodities and services. He determined that there is a big deficiency in the effective utilization of web services by these libraries to market their websites; he observed that these libraries were not using their websites effectively for marketing their library assets and services. To be more specific he pointed out that the websites of studied libraries have no link and online support services for free access to the library resources, information, and services to the users. He also noted that the library managers were also deficient in knowledge regarding the application of LIS marketing strategies to achieve the goals of the libraries. This suggests the necessity of launching awareness campaigns/ courses for library in-charges regarding the importance and application of marketing maneuvers.

Ifijeh (2011) at Nigeria concluded that there is a big need for the promotion of the concept of marketing in Nigerian university libraries to get the ends of delivery of information and services to the users of the libraries. He studied the library marketing practices and investigated major problems faced by the Nigerian University Libraries. In the light of his findings, he recommended some steps to cope with the identified issues. He argued that proper planning in respect of marketing library services would result in the improvement of the image of the libraries and would attract more clients to use library services. They tried to draw the attention of all stakeholders towards the importance of the application of LIS marketing strategies in Nigerian University libraries.

Johromi and Eerfanmanesh (2011) conducted a feasibility study regarding the implementation of the principles of marketing within the libraries of different universities in Tehran. He found an average level of understanding of the concept of Library marketing services amongst the thein-charges / managers of the libraries. The understanding of the elements of planning library marketing was found greater than the average level. Regarding the application of market mix, most of the librarians/ managers focused on the application of the 4ps component of marketing (product, place, promotion, and price). Moreover, research findings showed an average level of results regarding the probability of execution of principles of marketing.

Makori (2011) performed survey research to investigate the situation of marketing by services and merchandise in academic libraries in Kenya. The researcher observed that the current library marketing literature is mainly comprised of survey research and the professional experiences of the researchers. The author observed the effective utilization of marketing approaches as part and parcel of the management process regarding the promotion of library services and merchandise. Moreover, it was noticed by the researcher that university libraries of Kenya using marketing approaches were the best ones to fulfill the information needs of the users.

VIJ (2012) conducted a detailed review of the changes regarding the expansion of information society and transformational changes within libraries in India. He stated that the libraries of the present era were just like business industries where maximum efforts were made to deliver the services up to the best satisfaction of the customers /users. The author added that the marketing needs of Library merchandise and services had been raised because of high competence due to advanced technologies, high cost of maintenance, big expectations of the customers, and limited budgets. Successful LIS marketing depends upon the best strategic planning. The author recommended addressing all doings based on advanced technology, constraints and essentials of professional talents in the course of applying marketing strategies in Indian libraries.

IV. NATIONAL LEVEL RESEARCH STUDIES

Ameen (2011) highlighted the emergent need for activities to enhance the visibility of products and services of the Library and information professionals to attract the community. She argued that the marketing approach provides marvelous opportunities to professionals in the field of Library and Information science. The researcher explained that the philosophy, as well as tools of LIS marketing, could be supportive in creating visibility and scheming customer-specific services.

Shafique (2009) surveyed to investigate the information-related needs of the users/students. She used Marketing Research Approach to access the needs of the students of the Library science department. She suggested the utilization of some ways to deliver user-focused services, enhance the use of library services, and manage the budget constraints in libraries.

Tufail (2009) completed his research on the promotional component of the marketing mix approach in the university (academic) libraries in Lahore. She investigated the attitudes of professional librarians towards the utilization of promotional events to attract users and the effective utilization of library and information services. She reported the existence of an optimistic attitude of professional librarians towards the utilization of promotional activities in the delivery of library services. She added that though there existed a positive attitude towards the utilization of promotional activities in the marketing of Library services however most of the professional librarians were used marketing medium of personal communication for the promotion of library services and products in their working areas. She also concluded that the limited budget was the major reason for the poor utilization of promotional activities at their libraries.

Arshad (2009) conducted his M. Phil. research on the quality of services at Punjab University Libraries (PULs) through a survey questionnaire from library users. The researcher utilized SERVQUAL to investigate the user's level of understanding of concepts of LIS marketing and their anticipations from university libraries. He concluded that most of the user's expectations were about the presence of experienced staff, suitable library hours, and a good-looking display of library items/materials. The researcher concluded that a slightly positive score has existed towards Service quality at academic libraries however it was needed to be improved much more.

Khan and Bhatti (2012) produced a case study on the use of social networks to promote library and information services in Pakistan. To respond to the questionnaire, they used a questionnaire. Data were gathered from librarians and LIS scholars at the Islamic University of Bahawalpur and the Bahauddin Zakariya University of Multan. From 37 respondents, data were collected. The study's findings showed that respondents exhibited upbeat behavior, and the majority agreed that using social networks is essential for grabbing internet users' attention and facilitating

information exchange and distant learning. According to their report, respondents recommended using social media sites like Facebook, Wikis, LinkedIn, blogging, YouTube, and virtual communities to promote different library services. They noted that challenges with the use of social networks in Pakistan's libraries for the promotion of library applications and services included a shortage of electricity, insufficient education programs, and a lack of information, confidentiality, and identity fraud.

Khan (2012) emphasizes the respondent's favorable actions toward the promotion of library resources and services via social media. Social media can be used in libraries to promote its users' access to services, materials, events, and communication. The study's findings suggest that libraries should be altered to better suit the demands of its patrons. Internet access for libraries should be made available, and they should create websites and social media accounts. All issues that prevent social media use in libraries should be fixed, and librarians should receive training on how to use social media. Soroya (2012) investigated the perception of librarians towards LIS marketing as well as the application of LIS marketing techniques at academic libraries of the University of the Punjab, Lahore. Application of marketing mix were assessed using 6 Ps components of the marketing mix. The author concluded that the majority of librarians understand the concept of LIS marketing more or less especially the promotion component of the marketing mix, however, the application of the LIS marketing approach is much poor than the required standards. She also added no or insignificant measures were taken to arrange/develop the interiors of the libraries so that the users could be attracted to library services and products.

Soroya (2013) has reviewed the literature on the what, how, and why of marketing in LIS as well as research studies that range from focusing on a single library to a collection of libraries in a certain geographic area. The extent to which necessary marketing strategies should be used in libraries has been fully realized. The results of the studies on LIS marketing showed that although librarians approve the use of LIS marketing, they are cautious to put these strategies into reality. Numerous studies on LIS marketing have been carried out at the international level, but more thorough research on the subject is required in Pakistan. It is essential to accurately assess the strengths and flaws of user- and client-centered library services in the current modern era of librarianship. Ameen (2015) investigated the use of Public Relations and Publicity (PRP) by the public libraries in Lahore, Pakistan.

V. RESEARCH PROBLEM

The ongoing growth of university instructional and research programs involved the provision of advanced client-centered resources to these library units. Each year, university libraries invest enormous sums to expand their collections and properly provide library services. Yet they are of no use if they are not used to address the knowledge needs of library users. Efficient use of resources and services can be accomplished by a marketing strategy.

They can be added in the process of planning, creating, and providing suitable services and goods. It is also likely that attitudes towards the marketing of information goods and services between librarians and consumers will be known. Some of the university libraries are using different types of marketing techniques to attract users towards the use of library services. This study will investigate the need for marketing in university libraries of Lahore and explore the different techniques are in the practice of university libraries for marketing. Generally, all librarians are not fully technically sound for marketing university libraries. This study will highlight the problems faced by university librarians in the marketing of library services and collection. Moreover, this study will suggest which types of strategies can be used for the marketing of library services.

- *Research Questions:* The following are research questions of the study:
 - What are the needs for marketing in the university libraries?
 - What are the current techniques deployed by university libraries in the marketing of library and information services?
 - What are the challenges faced by librarians in the marketing of university libraries?
 - What are the methods used for enhancing the marketing of university libraries?

VI. METHODS AND PROCEDURES

To attain its goals, this study adopted a quantitative research methodology. One of the fundamental components of the research process is choosing the approach that will best help to achieve the study objectives. The most important research method used in social science research is survey research. Data from the population were gathered for the current study via survey research based on a web-based questionnaire. The current study's target demographic was Lahore-based librarians and library staff working at HEC-recognized universities. The research revealed that 142 librarians were employed by Lahore's HEC-recognized universities. The convenience sampling method has been employed in this study to target the specific population group where data would be collected. After reviewing the literature, a formal questionnaire was created. On 15 study respondents, pilot testing was carried out. In order to improve clarity, assess respondents' comprehension, and track the time required to complete the questionnaire, pilot testing was conducted. During the pilot study, several questionnaire items were added and other sentences were revised. After one last round of editing, Google form was used to create the questionnaire. The study's respondents also received this link through other WhatsApp and Facebook groups. Out of 142 responders, 127 provided the information. The data file in the Excel sheet was downloaded from Google Docs when the data collection phase was complete, and numbers were assigned to each response. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to enter the data and do analysis. The errors made when entering data into SPSS were fixed. Using SPSS software, the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, frequency and percentage counts,

means, standard deviations, and variance. T-test was also used to see whether public and private sector librarians' opinions differed.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results and discussion of the distributed instrument are presented. The mean and standard deviation score are discussed for each element.

A. Need for marketing in university libraries

The findings in Table 1 demonstrates the mean scores of the statements regarding the need for marketing in university libraries. The findings presented that two statements got Mean Score > 4.00 and six statements got Mean Score > 3.00. The results showed that respondents were agreed that marketing of university libraries required “to strengthen the interpersonal interaction between librarians and users” (Mean=4.11, SD=0.76), “to identify the information needs of users” (Mean=4.07, SD=0.90), “achieving a high degree of customer loyalty” (Mean=3.92, SD=0.83), “to educate users regarding importance of the library usage” (Mean=3.89, SD=0.88), and to “accomplish the aims of the library” (Mean=3.85, SD=0.99).

<i>Level</i>	<i>Means</i>	<i>SD</i>
To strengthen the interpersonal interaction between librarians and users	4.11	0.76
To identify the information needs of users	4.07	0.90
Achieving a high degree of customer loyalty	3.92	0.83
To educate users regarding importance of the library usage.	3.89	0.88
To accomplish the aims of the library	3.85	0.99
Enable users develop expertise to obtain information from...	3.79	0.80
To compete favorably with other information providers	3.74	0.94
Creation of a favorable atmosphere for students to learn and work	3.72	0.98

Table 1: Need for marketing in university libraries (N=127)

B. Techniques used for marketing of library services

The findings in Table 2 displays the mean scores of the statements regarding the techniques used for marketing of library services. The findings presented in table 2 showed that two statements got Mean Score > 4.00 and nine statements got Mean Score > 3.00. The outcomes show that majority of the respondents were agreed that sending letters to users about newly added services through “E-mail and text messages” (Mean=4.17, SD=1.04), “provision of electronic access to information” (Mean=4.15, SD=0.86), “having the representative in institutional functions for library marketing” (Mean=3.96, SD=1.10), and “use of leaflets and posters” (Mean=3.96, SD=1.03). The findings revealed that respondents responded that they “adopted social media applications for marketing” (Mean=3.91, SD=0.98) and doing marketing of library services to “increase interpersonal-relationship between staff and users” (Mean=3.78, SD=1.20).

<i>Level</i>	<i>Means</i>	<i>SD</i>
Sending letters to users about newly added services through E-mail and text messages	4.17	1.04
Provision of electronic access to information	4.15	0.86
Having representative in institutional functions for library marketing	3.96	1.10
Use of leaflets and posters	3.96	1.03
Use of social media applications	3.91	0.98
Increase interpersonal relationship between staff and users	3.78	1.20
Organizing training sessions for user education	3.75	1.04
Provision of suggestion boxes	3.52	1.17
Creation of a library web page	3.46	1.07
Exhibitions and display of new arrivals	3.26	1.29
One on one discussion with users	3.15	1.38

Table 2: Techniques used for the marketing of library services (N=127)

C. Challenges faced by librarians in the marketing of university libraries

Table 3 shows the mean scores of the statements regarding the challenges faced by librarians in marketing university libraries. The results show that six statements got Mean score > 3.00 and three statements got Mean Score < 3.00. The majority of the respondents were opined that “lack of knowledge in library professionals about library marketing” (Mean=3.51, SD=1.02), inadequate funding (Mean=3.36, SD=0.69), and “lack of effective communication between librarians and users” (Mean=3.24, SD=0.73), and “management does not understand the concept of library marketing” (Mean=3.18, SD=0.68). The findings showed that “Lack of IT infrastructure” (Mean=3.05, SD=0.91) and Lack of training in library marketing (Mean=3.03, SD=0.79) were also major problems faced by university libraries of Lahore in marketing.

<i>Level</i>	<i>Means</i>	<i>SD</i>
Lack of knowledge in library professionals about library marketing	3.51	1.02
In-adequate fund	3.36	0.69
Lack of effective communication between librarians and users	3.24	0.73
Management does not understand the concept of library marketing	3.18	0.68
Lack of IT infrastructure	3.05	0.91
Lack of training in library marketing	3.03	0.79
Lack of media access to the marketing of academic library services	2.91	0.59
Lack of facilities to market library services	2.70	0.59
Management does not have the marketing policy for libraries	2.68	0.63

Table 3: Challenges faced by librarians in marketing of university libraries (N=127)

D. Methods for enhancing the marketing of university libraries

The findings in Table 4 shows the mean scores of the statements regarding the strategies for enhancing the marketing of university libraries. The outcomes show that two statements got a Mean score > 4.00 and five statements got Mean Score > 3.00. The findings reveal that majority of the respondents agreed that through organizing trainings, “seminars and workshops to educate librarians on marketing of library services” (Mean=4.14, SD=0.35), “management should have a marketing policy” (Mean=4.00, SD=0.52), “librarians should be willing to market library services” (Mean=3.16, SD=1.15), and “provision of adequate facilities for marketing” (Mean=3.15, SD=1.21).

<i>Level</i>	<i>Means</i>	<i>SD</i>
Organizing trainings, seminars and workshop to educate librarians on marketing of library services	4.14	0.35
Management should have a marketing policy	4.00	0.52
Librarians should be willing to market library services	3.16	1.15
Provision of adequate facilities for marketing	3.15	1.09
Marketing should be inculcated in the library school’s curriculum	3.15	1.21
Library management should have a separate budget for marketing	3.08	1.12
A unit should be established for marketing library services	3.03	1.10

Table 4: Methods for enhancing the marketing of university libraries (N=127)

E. Innovative tools used for library marketing based on types of universities

The independent t-test was applied to investigate the significant difference among the opinions of respondents based on types of universities. However, the findings mentioned in table 4.6 revealed that no significant difference was found in the opinions of respondents from public and private universities.

<i>Innovative tools used for library marketing</i>	<i>Private</i>		<i>Public</i>		<i>Sig.</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	
Need for marketing in university libraries	3.83	0.67	3.95	0.69	0.32
Techniques used for marketing of library services	3.76	0.79	3.70	0.71	0.69
Challenges faced by librarians in marketing of university libraries	3.13	0.50	3.00	0.54	0.17
Strategies for enhancing the marketing of university libraries	3.41	0.84	3.35	0.84	0.67

Table 5: Innovative Tools used for Library Marketing based on Types of Universities (N=127)

F. Innovative tools used for library marketing based on gender

An independent t-test was applied to identify the significant difference in the opinion of respondents based on gender. The results of the independent t-test presented in table 6 revealed that no significant difference was found in the opinions of male and female respondents.

Innovative tools used for library marketing	Male		Female		Sig.
	M	SD	M	SD	
Need for marketing in university libraries	3.83	0.69	3.99	0.64	3.83
Techniques used for marketing of library services	3.73	0.65	3.74	0.94	0.96
Challenges faced by librarians in marketing of university libraries	3.08	0.48	3.06	0.60	0.81
Strategies for enhancing the marketing of university libraries	3.37	0.83	3.41	0.85	0.79

Table 6: Innovative Tools Used for Library Marketing based on Genders (N=127)

G. Independent T-test

The significant differences in respondents' judgments based on the sorts of universities were examined using an independent t-test. However, the results showed that there were no significant differences between respondents' perspectives from public and private universities. There was no clear difference between male and female respondents' perspectives, according to the independent t-test results. Therefore, more findings of the study are captured through the below research questions accordingly.

- Question 1: What are the needs for marketing in university libraries?

The present study found that marketing university libraries required strengthening the interpersonal interaction between librarians and users to identify the information needs of users, achieve a high degree of customer loyalty, educate users regarding the importance of library usage, and accomplish the aims of the library. The previous study by Makori (2011) confirmed that using marketing approaches was the best one to fulfill the information needs of the users.

- Question 2: What are the current techniques employed by university libraries in the marketing of library and information services?

This study discovered that university librarians were using techniques for library marketing including sending letters to users about newly added services through E-mail and text messages, provision of electronic access to information, having a representative in institutional functions for library marketing, and use of leaflets and posters. The findings revealed that respondents responded that they adopted social media applications for marketing and doing marketing library services to increase the interpersonal relationship between staff and users. The previous study of Khan and Bhatti (2012) is consistent with the current study. They reported the use of Facebook, Wikis, LinkedIn, Blogging, YouTube, and virtual communities for the promotion of various library resources.

- Question 3: Which types of challenges are faced by librarians in the marketing of university libraries?

The current study highlighted that lack of knowledge in library professionals about library marketing, inadequate fund, lack of effective communication between librarians and users, management does not understand the concept of library marketing, lack of IT infrastructure, and lack of training in library marketing were the major problems faced by university librarians of Lahore in the marketing of libraries. The past study of Kaba (2011) is consistent with the current study. He also noted that the library managers were also deficient in knowledge regarding the application of LIS marketing strategies to achieve the goals of the libraries.

- Question 4: What are the strategies used for enhancing the marketing of university libraries?

The results showed that the majority of respondents agreed that management should have a marketing policy, librarians should be willing to market library services and provide adequate marketing facilities in addition to organizing training, seminars, and workshops to educate librarians on the marketing of library services. The study by Khan (2012) also confirms that Internet access for libraries should be made available, and they should create websites and social media accounts. All issues that prevent social media use in libraries should be fixed, and librarians should receive training on how to use social media.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

The current study found that marketing university libraries required enhancing the relationships between librarians and patrons, determining the information needs of patrons, achieving a high level of customer loyalty, educating patrons about the value of library use, and achieving the library's objectives. The results showed that respondents admitted to using social media applications for marketing and promoting library services in order to improve the rapport between staff and patrons. Insufficient funding, a lack of IT infrastructure, poor communication between librarians and users, management that did not

understand the concept of library marketing, and a lack of knowledge among library professionals about library marketing were the main problems faced by university librarians in Lahore, according to this study. The research found that the majority of respondents agreed that management should have a marketing policy, librarians should be eager to promote library services, and there should be enough marketing facilities available to teach librarians how to promote library services through the organization of training, seminars, and workshops. The limitation of this study was conducted in universities in Lahore and the data was obtained from 36 public sector and private HEC recognizes universities in Lahore, therefore the study is bound to this boundary and the outcome hence narrowed to the study scope. The finds revealed that respondents responded that they were adopted social media applications for marketing and marketing library services to increase the personal relationship between staff and users.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that for library marketing, libraries need understand how to do it in a variety of ways. Additionally, they should continually learn new techniques to improve the caliber and variety of their goods and services in accordance with shifting customer demands. It is important to design workshops and seminars to educate those who have never studied marketing at any level. Universities and professional organizations should hold these programs for their librarians and other librarians. Not only librarians are required to do this, but programs should also be set up for front-line personnel to improve their marketing competencies. To create a collection that is centered on the needs of the customer and strengthen ties with those who use the library, formal SWOT analyses and surveys about the products and services should be carried out. Each library should design its home page and social networking pages and use as a strategic tool to improve awareness, advertise products /services, distribute and disseminate digital products and services. Closed shelving is used in 50% of libraries. To increase the use of information, libraries should have an open shelving system. Libraries should pay attention to ventilation and temperature control so that patrons can sit and study in comfort.

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